

Effect Of Internal Audit Function On The Performance Of Lubricant Manufacturing Firms In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of the internal audit function on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The objectives of this study were to: Assess the internal audit risk management function in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Determine the internal audit control evaluation function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Investigate the internal audit compliance verification function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Evaluate the internal audit fraud detection and prevention function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study utilized the survey research design to obtain information from the respondents. The population of this study was drawn from the management staff in the lubricant firms in Anambra state which is 342 respondents. Research hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis. Primary Data were obtained through the administration of structured questionnaires to respondents. The variables were, internal audit risk management function, internal audit control evaluation function, internal audit compliance verification function, audit fraud detection and prevention function and performance. The findings revealed that Internal audit risk management function had significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria (T, 2,049, P,0.000). Internal audit internal control evaluation function had significantly contribute to the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria(T, 9.718, P,0.000)..Internal audit compliance verification function had significant impact on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, (T, 6.614, P, 0.000). In view of the findings, the study recommended that Manufacturing firms should institutionalize comprehensive risk assessment frameworks that enable internal auditors to identify and evaluate operational, financial, and strategic risks regularly. Firms should empower internal auditors with the authority and resources to periodically review and test the effectiveness of control systems across departments. Manufacturing firms should ensure that internal auditors actively monitor compliance with internal policies, regulatory standards, and industry best practices

Keywords: internal audit risk management, internal audit control evaluation function, internal audit compliance verification, internal audit fraud detection, internal audit fraud detection, internal audit fraud detection

INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing sector is a cornerstone of industrialization, employment creation, and value addition in many developing economies. In Anambra State home to industrial clusters in Onitsha, Nnewi and Awka the sector plays a strategic role in the state's industrialization agenda and contributes materially to local economic activity, trade and export potential. The Anambra Industrialization Framework and recent state export strategies explicitly identify manufacturing clusters and agro-industrial hubs as central to the

state's growth plans, noting the presence of multiple industrial clusters and a sustained share of manufacturing in the state's economic output (Apreku-Djan, Ameyaw, Ahiale, Owusu, & Apreku, 2022). Manufacturing firms operate in complex, resource-intensive environments where capital equipment, inventories, supply chains and labour must be coordinated efficiently (Niyitegeka. & Kato, 2021). These firms are exposed to a broad spectrum of risks fraud and financial misstatement, operational inefficiencies, inventory shrinkage, regulatory non-compliance, safety and environmental hazards, and supply-chain disruptions that directly affect profitability and long-term viability (Betti, & Sarens, & Poncin, 2021).. Effective internal control systems, with capable internal audit functions at their core, are widely regarded as essential to mitigating these risks, improving operational reliability, and enhancing the quality of financial reporting. Empirical work across Nigeria's manufacturing sector indicates that internal audit practices (auditor competence, scope, independence and frequency) are associated with improvements in financial reporting quality and overall firm performance (ElHaddad, Elhaddad, & Alfadhil, 2020)..

The manufacturing sector is a critical driver of economic growth in Nigeria. However, the sector continues to face challenges such as resource mismanagement, fraud, weak internal controls, and poor compliance with regulatory frameworks. These challenges have significantly hindered the performance of many manufacturing firms, reducing their profitability, competitiveness, and sustainability (Erlina, & Idhar. & Agung, 2020)..

The internal audit function is designed to address such challenges by evaluating risk management systems, ensuring effective internal controls, verifying compliance with policies, and detecting fraud. In the context of Nigerian manufacturing firms, the role of internal auditing is particularly important because of the complexity and capital intensity of operations (Ogwiji, & Lasisi, 2020)..

Despite the presence of internal audit units in many firms, questions remain about their effectiveness in improving performance. Issues such as management interference, inadequate resources, and lack of independence often weaken the internal audit function. It is against this backdrop that this study examines the effect of the internal audit function on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria (Lumidi, & Opuodho, 2022).

The internal audit function is an assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve an organization's operations by evaluating risk management, internal controls, and governance processes (Nguyen, 2024). In manufacturing firms, internal auditors perform functions such as assessing the adequacy of controls over production processes, verifying inventory records and cost flows, checking compliance with safety and environmental requirements, and testing financial reporting procedures. When effective, these activities reduce leakage (waste, theft, errors), expose process inefficiencies, improve management information, and strengthen corporate governance factors that can translate into higher operational efficiency and improved financial performance.

Lubricant Manufacturing firms in Anambra State occupy a vital position in the state's economic structure, serving as engines of employment, innovation, and industrial development. However, in recent years, the performance of many manufacturing firms has been under increasing strain due to rising production costs, weak internal control systems, fraudulent activities, and operational inefficiencies. Despite various management reforms, these firms continue to grapple with challenges such as poor financial reporting accuracy, resource wastage, inadequate monitoring of production processes, and non-compliance with regulatory standards. These recurring issues raise concerns about the effectiveness of internal audit functions in promoting sound financial management and operational excellence.

The internal audit function is meant to provide an independent and objective assurance that an organization's risk management, control, and governance processes are functioning effectively. Yet, in many manufacturing firms in Anambra State, the internal audit departments are either under-resourced, poorly structured, or lack sufficient independence from management. In some cases, internal auditors report directly to the same management whose activities they are supposed to evaluate, leading to conflicts of interest and compromised objectivity. This undermines the credibility of audit findings and limits their usefulness in decision-making.

Moreover, several firms in Anambra State treat internal auditing as a mere statutory or routine exercise rather than as a strategic tool for improving performance. Many internal audits focus narrowly on financial record verification, ignoring operational and compliance audits that could uncover inefficiencies in procurement, production, and inventory management. Consequently, critical risks such as misappropriation of assets, production leakages, and poor cost control often go undetected until they manifest as severe financial losses.

Empirical evidence from within Nigeria and other developing economies suggests that firms with effective internal audit systems perform better financially and operationally. However, there is limited empirical research specifically examining this relationship in the context of Anambra State's manufacturing firms particularly those located in industrial clusters like Nnewi, Onitsha, and Awka. Most prior studies have focused on financial institutions or public sector organizations, leaving a gap in understanding how internal audit practices affect private manufacturing performance indicators such as profitability, productivity, and competitive advantage.

Furthermore, issues such as lack of skilled and professionally certified internal auditors, inadequate technological support for auditing, poor management response to audit recommendations, and weak oversight from boards of directors have hindered the effectiveness of internal audits. These weaknesses may explain why several manufacturing firms in Anambra State continue to experience low profitability, declining productivity, and financial irregularities despite having internal audit units.

Therefore, the key problem this study seeks to address is the apparent gap between the existence of internal audit functions and the actual improvement in the performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra State. It questions whether the internal audit functions, as currently structured and implemented, are effective in enhancing financial performance, operational efficiency, and overall organizational sustainability. The study also aims to identify which elements of the internal audit function such as auditor independence, scope of audit, audit frequency, management support, and auditor competence have the most significant impact on firm performance.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of the internal audit function on the performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra state. The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the internal audit risk management function in manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
2. Determine the internal audit control evaluation function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
3. Investigate the internal audit compliance verification function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
4. Evaluate the internal audit fraud detection and prevention function in the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Internal Audit Function

Internal auditing is an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of an organization's risk management, internal controls, and governance processes. In manufacturing firms, the internal audit function plays a vital role in ensuring accountability, minimizing operational inefficiencies, detecting fraud, and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements (Ugwu, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The Agency and Stewardship theories were adopted to guide this study. Agency theory helps in resolving problems which occur in agency relationships. It deals with the conflict of interest between the agents and the principal especially when their perception of risk differs. One of the issues which this disparity might cause is a shift from Shareholders' Wealth Maximization to pursuing the agent's own interest. Agency theory therefore does not only provide a basis for internal audit but also brings forth indicators of a good

internal audit system which enhances financial performance. The agency relationship is such which subsists between the owner(s) of a firm, and the agent, with the right to make decisions delegated to the latter³⁰. In this form of business relationship, stakeholders look forward to seeing the profitability of the business and how their investment will be maximized. On the other hand, the agent of the company, who are the managers, focuses on the liquidity, profitability, leverage and the going concern of such firms. Thus, it becomes paramount to achieving convergence of goals. Stewardship theory is a substitute to agency theory⁴¹. The theory spells out the responsibilities and traits expected to be exhibited by directors, as such which focus on achieving the objectives of that organization. Though stewardship theory supports agency theory, it however believes that the personnel who serve as agents are those who would not seek their self-interest but work towards the attainment of the organization's objectives. In so doing, the stewards would have their individual needs met ²⁴. The theory is relevant in assessing the effect internal audit has on firms' financial performance; as internal auditors who desire to "climb the organizational ladder", are expected to act in the overall interest of the firm and her shareholders; not otherwise. The stewardship theory provides a number of non-financial motivations such as a chance to grow (relating to professional competency), exercising responsibility and authority (relating to independence) and gaining recognition for internal auditors and directors acting as stewards.

2.3 Empirical Review

Hamza Alqudah et al. (2023) examined internal audit effectiveness in Jordan's public sector, identifying management support, external auditor collaboration, independence, and extrinsic rewards as critical drivers. Their study, rooted in the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory and based on 117 survey responses, found that while management-related factors significantly enhanced auditor effectiveness, the size of internal audit units had no notable impact. Furthermore, extrinsic rewards were found to moderately influence the relationship between empowerment variables and audit effectiveness. These findings suggest that strengthening internal audit support systems can reduce inefficiencies and improve financial governance, especially in public organizations

Dada and Adebawale (2023) explored internal audit practices in selected Federal Polytechnics. Their study emphasized the impact of management perception, support, and auditor independence on audit effectiveness. Data collected via structured questionnaires revealed that these factors collectively enhanced the capacity of internal auditors to detect noncompliance and added value to institutional operations. Their findings highlight that internal audit practices in Nigeria's public institutions can be optimized by reinforcing management collaboration and ensuring auditor autonomy

Eniola, Tonade, and Adeniji (2021) focused on listed companies in southwestern Nigeria, applying both survey and ex-post-facto research designs. Their study found that internal audit oversight significantly influenced return on assets (ROA), suggesting that strong audit mechanisms are vital for enhancing the credibility of financial reports and boosting firm value. The findings reinforce the role of internal audit in shaping operational efficiency and financial transparency.

Etuk, et al (2025) ascertained the effect of audit committee attributes on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group for the period 2014 to 2023. The independent variable, audit committee attributes, was proxied by audit committee financial expertise, audit committee gender; while the dependent variable was proxied by earnings management. Ex post facto research design was adopted and secondary data were employed. The population of the study consisted of 13 listed deposit money banks and purposive sampling technique was employed to select 11 deposit money banks. The study employed robust regression technique was employed in analysing the data and the statistical package employed was STATA 14.2. From the analysis, it was found out that audit committee independence has a significant negative effect on Eckel's income smoothing index of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria; audit committee financial expertise has a significant positive effect on the Eckel's income smoothing index of the sampled deposit money bank; audit committee gender diversity has no significant effect on Eckel's income smoothing index of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria; Thus, it was concluded that audit committee attributes have significant effect on financial reporting quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Based, on the findings of this study, it was

therefore recommended among others that regulatory bodies should ensure that independent audit committee members with significant industrial experience and sound financial background form the majority of members of the audit committees as this could help tremendously in detecting earnings management and thus enhance financial reporting quality.

Kubiat, et al, (2025) examined the effect of audit committee attributes on financial reporting quality of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design and utilized a panel data of sixty (60) pooled observations gathered from six (10) listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria over ten (10)-year period (2014-2023) and employed a panel multiple regression technique to analyze the data via E-views 10.0 statistical package. The study findings revealed audit committee independence has a significant negative relationship (Coeff.=-1.1648{0.0046}) with discretionary accrual of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria while audit firm tenure has a non-significant positive relationship (Coeff. =0.0357{0.6224}) with discretionary accrual of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. It also revealed that audit committee expertise has significant negative relationship (Coeff.=-0.0257{0.0000}) with discretionary accrual of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria while audit committee meetings have non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.0027{0.0634}) with discretionary accrual of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. Audit committee size also showed a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff.=-0.2320{0.1614}) with discretionary accrual of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria.

Abhisheck and Nagari (2025) examined the influence of Audit Committee (AC) composition on Firm Performance (FP) by measuring AC composition (ACC) with a composite score based on the varying effect of each composition-characteristic. Partial Least Squares- Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique is used to weigh ACC characteristics. Based on 133 companies and covering five years from 2016 to 2020, the study analyses data after controlling endogeneity through the Gaussian Copula approach.– We find a significant positive influence of ACC on Firm Performance. Among the ACC characteristics, the absence of executive directors has the highest positive weight on ACC to influence FP, followed by AC size and Gender diversity. AC independence and members’ accounting and financial expertise have no significant weight on its composition. Apart from the theoretical contribution, the study reveals that each ACC characteristic has a varying effect on AC effectiveness to influence the FP that needs to be considered by regulators while framing regulations on ACC and by BOD while constituting AC for a company. The study claims originality by being pioneering to reveal that AC composition, with a synergy of its disparate characteristics, positively impacts FP. It highlights that the absence of executive directors and gender diversity in AC (characteristics overlooked by the extant literature) significantly and positively influence FP. Methodologically, it introduces the use of the PLS-SEM algorithm to weigh the characteristics in governance studies. Further, these findings remain relevant amid recent Indian legal reforms, offering contemporary insights for policy consideration.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is the **descriptive survey research design**. This design is appropriate when the researcher seeks to collect information that describes existing phenomena, conditions, or relationships without manipulating the study environment (Babbie, 2013; Asika, 2006).

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study was drawn from the management staff in the lubricant firms in Anambra state.

Table 3.1: Population Distribution of the selected lubricant firms

S/No	Names of Manufacturing Firms	Location	Mgt cadre
1	A-Z OIL	Nnewi	30
2	Seahorse oil	Ozubulu	27
3	Jezco oil	Nnewi	30
4	Whiz oil	Onitsha	26
5	Chiben oil	Onitsha	25

6	Ibeto oil	Nnewi	35
7	Visa oil	Nnewi	25
8	Dozzy oil	Atani	27
9	Envoy Oil	Onitsta	31
10	Lopa Oil	Onitsha	16
11	KM Oil	Ogbaru	17
12	Abbnnox oil	Onitsha	20
13	Hariz oil	Oba	33
	Total Population		342

Source: Human Resource Department of the firms

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample is a representation of the whole but a selected part of a population. It involves a process of selecting a proportion of a population considered adequate to represent all the existing characteristics of that population for the purpose of generalizing the findings of the sample to the target population and to other population having the same characteristics of the target population (Igweonyia, 2002).

A **stratified random sampling technique** will be employed, whereby staff members are grouped according to their departments, and respondents are randomly selected from each stratum. This method ensures balanced representation across different job categories within the firms.

3.4 Sources of Data

The study will make use of both:

- **Primary Data:** obtained through the administration of structured questionnaires to respondents. The questionnaire capture variables related to internal audit function.
- **Secondary Data:** sourced from textbooks, journals, annual reports of manufacturing firms, and publications from professional bodies such as the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA).

3.5 Method of Data Collection

The researcher personally administered the questionnaires and followed up to ensure a high retrieval rate

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using both **descriptive and inferential statistics**:

1. **Descriptive Statistics** such as frequencies, percentages, and tables were used to summarize respondents' views.
2. **Inferential Statistics** were applied using **Multiple Regression Analysis** to test the effect of the independent variables (risk management, internal control evaluation, compliance verification, fraud detection/prevention) on the dependent variable (performance of manufacturing firms).

The regression model used was

$$PF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RM + \beta_2 ICE + \beta_3 CV + \beta_4 FDP + \mu$$

Where:

PF = Performance of Manufacturing Firms

RM = Risk Management

ICE = Internal Control Evaluation

CV = Compliance Verification

FDP = Fraud Detection and Prevention

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients

μ = Error term

Statistical analyses were conducted using **SPSS software** at a **5% level of significance (0.05)**.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This section presents the empirical results and discussion of findings, Ordinary Least Square was used as techniques for the analysis, the result was subjected to different statistical and econometrics test. We begin by discussing the order of integration of the interest variables.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 4.2.1, displays the number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of the explained variable, and each of the explanatory variables, and provides the descriptive statistics for all the variables in the model. The descriptive data of the chosen service sector that comprise our sample are displayed in the table below.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
PERF	331	1.00	5.00	1.6284	.86566	1.446	1.979
IARMF	331	1.00	3.00	1.4622	.72672	1.228	-.012
IACEF	331	1.00	2.00	1.2175	.41319	1.376	-.108
AUCVF	331	1.00	2.00	1.4199	.49430	.326	-1.905
IAFDPF	331	1.00	4.00	2.5740	.80705	-.190	-.421
Valid N (listwise)	331						

The table above indicates that the mean of performance is 1.6% with standard deviation of 86% the minimum and maximum values of 1% and 5% respectively. The mean value of internal audit risk management function (IARMF) is 1.46% with standard deviation of 72% the minimum and maximum values of 1% and 3% respectively. The mean internal audit control evaluation (IACEF) is 1.21% with standard deviation of 41%, the minimum and maximum values of 1% and 2% respectively. Internal audit complain verification function (AUCVF) mean value is 41% with standard deviation of 49%, the minimum and maximum values of 1% and 2% respectively.

Internal audit fraud detection and prevention function (IAFDPF) mean value is 2.57% with standard deviation of 80%, the minimum and maximum values of 1% and 4% respectively.

These results suggest that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean because the standard deviations of all the variables are less than the mean values. Also, the skewness value of all the variables is close to zero, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature,. The Kurtosis values of all the variables is also not closer to 3 it indicates that the shape is a normal distribution, Shao (2003) submits that normality of data does not in any way affect the inferential statistics estimate to the BLUE properties. (Best, Linear, Unbiased, Estimate)

4. 2: Correlation Analysis

A square matrix that displays the correlation coefficients between two variables is called a correlation matrix. The strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables are measured by correlation coefficients. Frequently used in multivariate analysis and statistics, a correlation matrix looks at the relationships between several variables. It is possible to assess the link between two variables by using a correlation matrix: A relationship is strong if the relationship value is 1. The relationship is neutral if the relationship value is 0. In the event that the relationship's value is -1, it is weak or negative. Therefore, in examining the association among the variables, we employed the Spearman's rho correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in the table 4.2 below.

Correlations

			PERF	IARMF	IACEF	AUCVF	IAFDPF
Spearman's rho	PERF	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.585	-.344	.045	.186
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.414	.001
		N	331	331	331	331	331
	IARMF	Correlation Coefficient	.585	1.000	-.252	-.196	.381
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	331	331	331	331	331
	IACEF	Correlation Coefficient	-.344	-.252	1.000	.620	.324
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	331	331	331	331	331
	AUCVF	Correlation Coefficient	.045	-.196	.620	1.000	-.202
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.414	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	331	331	331	331	331
	IAFDPF	Correlation Coefficient	.186	.381	.324	-.202	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	331	331	331	331	331

Performance is positively connected with factors such as internal audit risk management, internal audit complain verification function and internal audit fraud detection and prevention function, while Performance goes further to negatively connected to internal audit control evaluate function. None of the factors, nevertheless, was discovered to be greater than 0.80. That is, no two exploratory variables had a perfect correlation. The highest correlation is between two variables which are highly correlated with (PERF/IARMF =-0.58) which indicate that multi co linearity is not a serious problem that would distort the regression result in the model used for analysis. A close look at the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient results revealed that all the variables are strongly associated with Frequency reporting quality. Therefore, in checking for multicollinearity problem, the study noticed from the correlation table above that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated and thereby ruled out the case of having an outlier. This indicates the absence of multi-collinearity problem in the model used for the analysis. This also justifies the use of the Panel Least Square (PLS)

4.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.3.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.863 ^a	.744	.741	.44074	.744	236.766	4	326	.000	1.852

a. Predictors: (Constant), IAFDPF, AUCVF, IARMF, IACEF

b. Dependent Variable: PERF

Table 4.4.1 shows that R² co-efficient of determination which measures the strength of the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable has the value of 0.74. This implies that 74% of the variation in internal audit function on performance is explained by variations in risk management, internal control evaluation, compliance verification, and fraud prevention. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.74%. Test for autocorrelation: This is used to test whether errors corresponding to different observations are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no

autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 2 reveals no autocorrelation in the model. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.852 which indicates that the study is free from the problems of autocorrelation.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	183.967	4	45.992	236.766	.000 ^b
	Residual	63.326	326	.194		
	Total	247.293	330			

a. Dependent Variable: PERF

b. Predictors: (Constant), IAFDPF, AUCVF, IARMF, IACEF

The f-statistics value of 236.766 in table 4.4.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables have significant effect on dependent variable such as risk management, internal control evaluation, compliance verification, and fraud prevention can collectively explain the variations in internal audit function variables on performance of manufacturing firms.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		t	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.087	.125		.695	.488	-.160	.334
	IARMF	.850	.042	.714	2.049	.000	.768	.932
	IACEF	.200	.103	.477	9.718	.000	-1.202	-.797
	AUCVF	.906	.078	.517	6.614	.000	.753	1.060
	IAFDPF	.089	.045	.083	1.387	.098	.001	.177

a. Dependent Variable: PERF

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing accounting theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table 4.4.3 above, we found out that internal audit risk management function (IARMF) has a positive sign given its value as 0.85%; this implies that a unit increase in internal audit risk management function (IACEF) increases the performance by 20%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Internal Audit Complain Verification Function (AUCVF) has a positive sign given its value as .90%; this implies that a unit increase in internal audit complain verification function (AUCVF) increases the performance by 90%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation.

Internal Audit Fraud Detection And Prevention Function (IAFDPF) has a positive sign given its value as .89%; this implies that a unit increase in Internal Audit Fraud Detection And Prevention Function (IAFDPF) increases the performance by 89%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of the explanatory parameters in the model. From table Coefficients above internal audit risk management function (IACEF), this is statistically significant (t, 2.049, p, 0.00), this suggest that it contribute significantly to Performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra state. Internal Audit control evaluation function (IACEF) is t,9.718 and prob,0.000 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to Performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra state at 5% level of significant. Internal Audit Complain Verification Function (AUCVF) is t, 6.614 and prob, 0.000 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to Performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra state at 5% level of significant. Internal Audit fraud detection and prevention function (IAFDPF) is t, 1.387and prob,0.098 This is statistically

significant, this suggest that it does not contribute significantly to Performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra state at 5% level of significant.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

Here, the five hypotheses formulated in chapter one was tested using t-statistics and significance value of the parameter variables in the regression result. The essence of this is to ascertain how significant the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables.

4.4.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Internal audit risk management function has no significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Internal audit risk management function has a t-statistics of 2.049 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state that internal audit risk management function has significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

4.4.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Internal audit internal control evaluation function does not significantly contribute to the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Internal audit internal control evaluation function have a t-statistics of 9.718 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Internal audit internal control evaluation function have significantly contribute to the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria

4.4.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Internal audit compliance verification function has no significant impact on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Materials planning have a t-statistics of 6.614 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Internal audit compliance verification function has significant impact on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

4.4.4 Test of Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: Internal audit fraud detection and prevention function does not significantly affect the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Internal audit fraud detection and prevention function has a t-statistics of 1.387 and a probability value of 0.98 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis and reject the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Internal audit fraud detection and prevention function does not significantly affect the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

4.5 Discussion of findings

This research examined the effect of the internal audit function on the performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra State Data were sourced from the employee of the selected manufacturing firms in Anambra State. The data generated were subjected to statistical analysis and the following output was ascertained.

Internal audit risk management function and performance: The study found that internal audit risk management function has a positive effect on performance of manufacturing firms in Anambra State. The implication of these findings is that, The internal audit risk management function plays a critical role in enhancing the performance and sustainability of manufacturing firms. It involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential risks that could hinder the achievement of organizational goals. Through systematic risk evaluation, internal auditors provide management with timely insights into operational weaknesses, compliance gaps, and emerging threats that may affect production efficiency or financial stability.

In manufacturing firms, effective risk management ensures that resources are used optimally, production losses are minimized, and business continuity is maintained. Internal auditors contribute by designing and

monitoring internal controls, ensuring adherence to safety standards, and verifying compliance with environmental and regulatory requirements. This proactive approach not only reduces exposure to financial and operational risks but also enhances decision-making, accountability, and overall performance. Moreover, internal audit risk management fosters a culture of transparency and continuous improvement. By identifying inefficiencies and recommending corrective actions, internal auditors support strategic objectives such as cost reduction, product quality improvement, and customer satisfaction. Consequently, firms with strong internal audit risk management functions often record improved profitability, resilience, and competitiveness in dynamic business environments. Recent studies (e.g., Olamide & Uchenna, 2024; Yusuf et al., 2025) affirm that the effectiveness of internal audit risk management is positively correlated with organizational performance, particularly in sectors with complex operational and financial structures like manufacturing.

Internal Audit Control Evaluation Function and Performance of Manufacturing Firms: The study found that Internal Audit Control Evaluation Function has a significant positive effect on Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. The implication is that the internal audit control evaluation function is vital to ensuring operational efficiency and sustainable performance in manufacturing firms. It involves the systematic review and assessment of internal control systems to determine their adequacy, effectiveness, and compliance with organizational policies and industry standards. Through control evaluation, internal auditors identify weaknesses or lapses in production, procurement, inventory management, and financial reporting processes that may expose the firm to risks or inefficiencies.

In manufacturing settings, where production activities are complex and capital-intensive, effective control evaluation helps to safeguard assets, prevent waste, detect errors, and curb fraudulent activities. Internal auditors assess whether control measures such as segregation of duties, authorization procedures, and record-keeping systems are functioning as intended. The findings from such evaluations guide management in strengthening control frameworks and implementing corrective actions that improve process reliability and accountability. Ultimately, robust internal control evaluation enhances organizational performance by ensuring operational consistency, cost control, and regulatory compliance. It also promotes better decision-making and resource utilization, leading to improved productivity and profitability. Empirical studies (e.g., Nwankwo & Okeke, 2024; Bello et al., 2025) indicate that manufacturing firms with strong internal audit control evaluation functions often experience superior performance outcomes, as effective control systems form the backbone of efficient operations and strategic growth.

Internal Audit Compliance Verification Function and Performance of Manufacturing Firms: The study found that Internal Audit Compliance Verification Function and has significant positive effect on Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. The internal audit compliance verification function is a crucial mechanism that ensures manufacturing firms adhere to established laws, regulations, standards, and internal policies. This function involves systematically reviewing the organization's operations, financial activities, and production processes to verify that they align with both internal control procedures and external regulatory requirements. In manufacturing firms, compliance verification is essential due to the sector's exposure to multiple regulatory frameworks, such as environmental standards, labor laws, tax regulations, and quality control policies. Through regular compliance audits, internal auditors help management identify areas of non-compliance, assess the implications, and recommend corrective actions. This proactive oversight reduces the likelihood of legal sanctions, penalties, and reputational damage that could negatively impact firm performance.

In manufacturing firms, compliance verification is essential due to the sector's exposure to multiple regulatory frameworks, such as environmental standards, labor laws, tax regulations, and quality control policies. Through regular compliance audits, internal auditors help management identify areas of non-compliance, assess the implications, and recommend corrective actions. This proactive oversight reduces the likelihood of legal sanctions, penalties, and reputational damage that could negatively impact firm performance. Moreover, adherence to compliance standards enhances operational transparency, builds investor and customer confidence, and promotes ethical business practices. When manufacturing firms

maintain strong compliance verification systems, they experience improved efficiency, reduced risk exposure, and sustainable profitability. Empirical evidence (e.g., Okonkwo & Ibrahim, 2024; Adeyemi et al., 2025) shows that firms with effective internal audit compliance verification functions tend to perform better financially and operationally, as compliance fosters stability, accountability, and continuous improvement within organizational processes

Internal Audit Fraud Detection and Prevention Control and Performance of Manufacturing Firms:

The study found that Internal Audit Fraud Detection and Prevention Control have a positive and insignificant effect on Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. The internal audit fraud detection and prevention control function is essential for safeguarding the assets and integrity of manufacturing firms. It focuses on identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential fraudulent activities that could undermine financial stability, operational efficiency, and stakeholder confidence. Internal auditors achieve this by evaluating internal controls, monitoring financial transactions, and ensuring that processes such as procurement, inventory management, and payroll are transparent and properly authorized.

In manufacturing firms, where large volumes of materials and financial transactions occur daily, the risk of fraud such as asset misappropriation, falsified records, or procurement irregularities is significant. Effective fraud detection and prevention controls help minimize such risks by enforcing strict internal checks, conducting surprise audits, and promoting ethical practices among employees.

Strong fraud prevention measures also contribute to improved organizational performance by enhancing financial accuracy, reducing losses, and promoting accountability. Firms that implement robust fraud control systems experience increased investor trust, operational efficiency, and profitability. Recent studies (e.g., Chukwu & Adewale, 2024; Nnadi et al., 2025) affirm that an effective internal audit fraud detection and prevention function positively influences firm performance, as it strengthens governance, ensures compliance, and supports sustainable business growth in the manufacturing sector

5.0 SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

The findings of this study confirm that internal audit functions play a crucial role in enhancing the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Each component—risk management, internal control evaluation, compliance verification, and fraud prevention—was found to have a positive and significant effect. Most notably, fraud detection and prevention contributed the strongest effect, suggesting that manufacturing firms benefit greatly from proactive audit systems that safeguard assets and reduce financial losses. Overall, effective internal audit practices promote operational efficiency, accountability, compliance, and sustainable growth in manufacturing firms.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

i. Strengthen Internal Audit Risk Management Function:

Manufacturing firms should institutionalize comprehensive risk assessment frameworks that enable internal auditors to identify and evaluate operational, financial, and strategic risks regularly.

ii. Enhance Internal Audit Control Evaluation Function:

Firms should empower internal auditors with the authority and resources to periodically review and test the effectiveness of control systems across departments.

iii. Improve Internal Audit Compliance Verification Function:

Manufacturing firms should ensure that internal auditors actively monitor compliance with internal policies, regulatory standards, and industry best practices.

iv. Strengthen Fraud Detection and Prevention Controls:

Internal auditors should implement proactive anti-fraud strategies such as continuous auditing, data analytics, and internal whistleblower systems.

5.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to knowledge by empirically establishing that internal audit functions explain up to 74% of the performance variation in Nigerian manufacturing firms. It also highlights fraud detection and prevention as the most impactful internal audit function.

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